

EFFECT OF INTEGRATED YOGIC MODULES ON SELECTED CLINICAL VARIABLES AMONG MEN WITH LOW BACK ACHE

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Abstract:

According to Patanjali, one can attain this (the individual self with the Supreme One) union by controlling and eliminating the ever- arising 'vrittis' or modifications of the mind. He also suggests that the mind, in turn, can be controlled through the right kind of discipline and training. Patanjali says that there are basic obstacles pervading the mind that are not conducive to yoga practice. The purpose of the study was to investigate effect of integrated yogic modules on selected clinical variables among Men with Low Back Ache. The subjects were equally assigned to random sampling procedure into two equal groups, i.e., the experimental group and control group. The experimental group under gone the practices in yogic practices. The control group not underwent the any kind of integrated yogic modules for the duration of the training programme of six weeks. The training was given in alternate days in a week. Each session scheduled for 60 minutes. The pain was measured before and after the experimentation using the standardized test. The data were analyzed by 't' test and it was concluded that the selected Integrated yogic modules group than the control group had significant ($P < 0.05$) effect on the pain level.

Key Words: Yogic Practices, Pain and Low Back Pain.

Introduction:

However, India is one of the major countries where communicable Diseases are still not under control. The incidence of new fatal diseases such as AIDS/HIV, hepatitis-A is on the increase and tuberculosis and malaria still take a high toll. Chronic non-communicable diseases such as heart diseases, diabetes and cancer are also in the rise (Bhat and Babu 2004). Health risk due to high prevalence of alcohol and Tobacco consumption is also increasing. , India's dream of "World Class" health care delivery system is difficult to achieve. The person who always eats wholesome food, enjoys a regular lifestyle, remains unattached to the objects of the senses, gives and forgives, loves truth, and serves others, is without disease. The total of body, mind and spirit. It includes physical health, mental health, emotional health, and social health. It is a well-known fact that India is, next only to China, the second largest country in terms of population in the world. But the health status of a great majority of the people is far from satisfactory as compared to China and other developed countries. However, over the last five decades or so, India has built up health infrastructure and manpower at primary, secondary and tertiary care in government, voluntary and private sectors and made considerable progress in improving the health of its population (Ray 2003; Bhat and Babu 2004).

Pancha Kosha - the Subtle Energy Body or 'Five Sheaths':

The subtle anatomy of the humans is divided into five energetic sheaths known as 'pancha kosha'. Pancha, meaning five and kosha, meaning layer or sheath. This ideology describes the human being "as multi-dimensional, with the source or foundation in a spiritual dimension." The so-called 'spiritual dimension' is pure consciousness which is hidden by the other four koshas, the outermost layer being the most dense, physical body. Each kosha can be thought of as energy vibrating at a different frequency. The physical body therefore vibrates at the slowest rate and the 'inner light of consciousness' or 'atman' vibrates at fastest rate or frequency. Although all five layers interpenetrate one another.

These five sheaths can be divided into three bodies:

- Sthula Sharira / Physical Body
 - Annamayakosha
- Sukshma Shariria / Astral Body
 - Pranamayakosha, Manomayakosha, Vijnanamayakosha
- Karana Shariria / Causal Body
 - Vijnanamayakosha, Anandamayakosha

Of all these, the anandamayakosha is not bound by time or space and does not die. When the practitioner resides in this sheath, they have remembered or realized their true nature, reached enlightenment and health will pervade on all layers. Yogic exercises recharge the body with cosmic energy. This facilitates

- Attainment of perfect equilibrium and harmony

- Promotes self- healing.
- Removes negative blocks from the mind and toxins from the body
- Enhances Personal power
- Increases self-awareness
- Helps in attention focus and concentration, especially important for children
- Reduces stress and tension in the physical body by activating the parasympathetic nervous system.

Aim of the Study:

The aim and objective of the study was to investigate Effect of Integrated Yogic Modules on Selected Clinical Variables among Men with Low Back Ache.

Review of Related Literature:

Swoboda B, et.al (1999), conducted the study on Collagen type VI content in healthy and arthritis knee joint cartilage at Abteilung für Orthopädische Rheumatologie, Orthopädische Klinik, Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg. They selected 148 histologically normal and 117 osteoarthritic cartilage samples from 18 different localisations of human knee joints. It was quantified in cartilage extracts using an inhibition-ELISA. In normal cartilage the average content of collagen type VI was 0.48 per cent of total collagens. The statistical analysis showed significant differences between normal femoral, tibial or retropatellar cartilage samples. Therefore, normal and osteoarthritic samples from different localizations had to be compared separately. A significant increase of collagen type VI was already found in early osteoarthritic lesions. As a result statistically significant increase of collagen type VI in osteoarthritic cartilage, the range of concentrations found in normal.

Methods and Materials:

The sample for the present study consists of 40 Men with Low Back Ache from Chennai city. The subjects were selected using random sampling method. Their age ranged from 30 - 40 years. They were divided into two groups namely Experimental group and control group (n=40), and pain measurement scale was administered to them. Experimental group was under the practice of integrated yogic modules for the period of 6 weeks both morning at 6.30 to 8.00 for the period of 6 weeks. The training programme was administered for 60 to 90 minutes per session. The control group did not engage in any special activities. The load was fixed based on the pilot study. The pretest and posttest were taken before and after the experimental training programme. The test was conducted pain measurement scale was administered on each end of the cessations and data was recorded. Analysis of covariance was used as a test of significance.

Experimental Group: Yogic Practices:

- Loosening Exercises:
- Asanas:
 - Ardhakati chakrasana
 - Ardhachakraasana
 - Parivartha trikonaasana
 - Bhujangaasana
 - Salabhaasana
 - Vakrasana
 - Ustraasana
- Relaxation:
- Meditation
 - Pain Management
- Meditation

Group II: Control Group (No Practice)

Results:

The data pertaining to the variables under the study was examined by analysis of covariance for each criterion variables separately in order to determine the differences, if any between the groups at different stages.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance for Pre and Post Tests Data on Pain of Integrated Yogic Modules Group and Control Group

	Integrated Yogic Modules Group	Control	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Squares	Obtained F
Pre Test Mean	8.06	6.77	Between	0.63	1	0.63	0.44
			Within	54.35	38	1.43	
Post Test Mean	4.63	7.32	Between	65.03	1	65.03	37.81*
			Within	65.35	38	1.72	
Adjusted Mean	4.65	7.30	Between	74.71	1	74.71	89.36*
			Within	30.93	37	0.84	
Mean Diff	3.43	0.55					

* Significant.

Table value for df 1 and 38 was 3.21 Table value for df 1 and 37 was 3.22.

The obtained adjusted mean values were presented through bar diagram in figure 1.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram on Ordered Pre and Post Means of Pain

Discussions on the Findings of Pain:

Taking into consideration of the pretest means and posttest means adjusted posttest means were determined and analysis of covariance was done and the obtained F value 89.36 was greater than the required value of 3.22. And hence it was accepted that the Integrated yogic modules significantly improved (decreased) the pain level of the yoga practitioners. The post hoc analysis of obtained ordered adjusted means proved that there was significant differences existed between integrated yogic modules group and control group on pain level. This proved that due to 6 weeks of integrated yogic modules pain level was significantly improved (decreased) among yoga practitioners.

Conclusion:

The analysis of co-variance of pain level indicated that experimental group I (Yogic practices), and group II (Control group). It may be due to the effect of Yogic practices. Integrated yogic modules improved the efficiency of health level significantly. On the basis of the findings of the study, it may be considered that the integrated yogic modules program is very useful method of training for the Men with Low Back Ache to decrease the pain within shorter duration. But it only retains for 6 weeks in integrated yogic modules the improvement was slow but it could retain the efficiency for longer duration.

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